

Studies on Emulsions of Guggal, Gandhbiroza, Salai, Rumi-Mastiki and Dhavda

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A comparative study of the stability coefficients of these five medically important gums reveals that dhavda produces most stable O/W emulsions with kerosene, benzene, olive oil except in case of castor oil. Guggal gum also produces stable emulsions with these systems but stability coefficient value is less than half that in case of dhavda gum. Rumi mastiki produces stable O/W emulsions only in case of kerosene oil and benzene, stability co-efficients being nearly equal to the stability coefficients of guggal gum stabilised emulsions. In case of other two systems reverse type of emulsions were produced. Gandhbiroza and salai gums can not be recommended for production of emulsions in case of kerosene oil, in the rest of the systems these two substances produced W/O type of emulsions.

MUKERJEE and Shukla^{1,2} have studied a large number of Indian gums and have also tried to compare the efficiency of some of the emulsions stabilised by certain gums. The present study has been undertaken because of the fact that almost no work has been done on the emulsifying property of these gums and oleo resin gums which can be used as effective medicines in the form of emulsions due to tremendous increase in the surface area on emulsion formation. The gums which have been described as good medicines³⁻⁸ for so many diseases can be used in small quantities in the form of emulsions of vegetable oils. The gums studied are as follows :

1. *Commiphora mukul* Engl. (guggal gum).
2. *Pinus roxburghii* Sargent 203 (sala dhup or gandhbiroza).
3. *Boswellia serrata* Roxb (H-Luban, B-salai gum).
4. *P. lentiscus* Linn (H. Rumi mastiki or B. Rumi mastungi).
5. *Anogeissus latifolia* Wall (H.-Bakla, Dhaura, B. O.-Dhavada)

Experimental

Purification of gums: The crude gums were dried in vacuo at about 100° and then powdered in a pestle and mortar. The powdered gums were then purified by methods⁹ described earlier. One percent suspension of each gum was made by heating the gum with distilled water on a water bath ; some of them which were not soluble in water were triturated with water.

The emulsions were prepared by the Agent-in-water method⁴ to contain 40% oil. The size frequency analysis has been done immediately and at different intervals of time by the method of King and Mukerjee⁵. The change of specific surface has been plotted against time as abscissa for several emulsions to illustrate the

agreement between the data on the change of specific surface with time and the exponential hypothesis. The lines are determined by fitting the data to the equation :

$$-\frac{d\sigma}{dt} = K'\sigma = \frac{\sigma}{k}$$

(where σ = specific surface, K' = instability coefficient, and K = stability coefficient) by the method of least squares². The curves representing the degradation of the emulsions are all linear ; hence a measure of the slope provides a quantitative comparison of stability. Accordingly the slope of each curve has been measured and divided by the graphically determined initial inter-face [σ_0] to furnish the rate of decrease per unit area of interface. This is termed the instability factor and might be defined as decrease of each cm² of fresh emulsion per day. The reciprocal of this would be a direct measure of emulsion stability (K).

Results and Discussion

The results of size frequency analysis are too numerous to quote in full but a representative selection is given in Table 1. The number of emulsions refer to the summarised results of Table 2, the suffix to the length of time in weeks, which elapsed between emulsification and analysis. In all these cases the emulsions had been homogenised.

TABLE 1—PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF OIL DROPLETS OF DIFFERENT SIZES IN HOMOGENISED EMULSION. (INDICES OVER THE EMULSIONS DENOTE THE NO. OF WEEKS THAT HAVE ELAPSED)

Mean diameter (in microns)	50.0	5.0-48	51.0	52.0	54.0	56.0	58.0
4	53.61	—	53.2	53.17	46.46	40.77	39.85
8	26.00	—	25.2	25.0	26.29	27.34	25.95
12	16.05	—	15.9	14.92	19.76	16.57	16.45
16	4.34	—	5.8	6.91	7.49	9.94	11.20
20	—	—	—	—	—	5.38	6.55
Free oil (P. C.)							nil
Agent = 1.0% Dhavda Gum							
Oil = Kerosene oil							

Size frequency analysis of 1.0% guggal gum stabilised emulsions reveals that the dispersions of globules are generally coarse as compared to soap stabilised emulsions of King and Mukerjee¹. O/W type of emulsions were produced with kerosene, olive, castor oils and also with benzene. Practically determined as well as graphically determined initial specific area values indicate that fine emulsions were produced in all cases except in case of kerosene oil as the internal phase. The stability coefficient values as well as the initial specific area values decrease in the same order as follows :

Olive oil > benzene > castor oil > kerosene oil

The stability coefficients of the emulsions of this gum in cases of benzene and castor oil can be compared with the stability coefficient of emulsion stabilised by *lannea grandis* gum in case of kerosene oil, previously found by Mukerjee and Shukla².

TABLE 2

Emul-Emulsifier sion	Graphically determined initial sp. area $\sigma_0 \times 10^8$ sqcm/gm oil	Practically determined initial sp. area sq. cm/ gm oil	Type of emulsion produced	Stability coefficient $K \times 10^8$
Data for 40% kerosene oil emulsions				
1 Guggal gum	5.62	7.82	o/w	6.03
4 Rumi mastiki	6.46	12.31	o/w	17.53
5 Dhavda	7.08	6.54	o/w	40.15
Data for 40% Benzene emulsions				
6 Guggal Gum	8.13	8.67	o/w	15.95
8 Salai gum	6.12	8.17	o/w	5.71
9 Rumi mastiki	6.08	7.55	o/w	10.11
10 Dhavda	8.91	6.93	o/w	41.95
Data for 40 % Olive Oil emulsions				
11 Guggal gum	9.33	12.18	o/w	20.01
15 Dhavda	6.79	9.26	o/w	42.21
Data for 40 % Castor Oil emulsions				
16 Guggal gum	7.76	10.05	o/w	15.56
20 Dhavda	3.43	4.68	o/w	15.01

The medicinal properties of this gum have been described in detail by Dastur⁶. These emulsions of vegetable oils stabilised by this agent may be used for all those purposes with more effectiveness.

Gandhbiroza, according to Dastur⁶ is stimulant, stomachic and diuretic. It is given in gleet, gonorrhoea and other disorders of the genito-urinary organs. The resin is a useful dressing for foul ulcers, buboes and abscesses.

The emulsion with kerosene oil was not possible while the other three systems gave reverse type of emulsions (w/o). These can also be utilised in the form of ointments.

Salai—Like Guggal salai also has numerous medicinal uses as given by Dastur^{6,7}. The emulsion with kerosene oil was not possible. Emulsions produced with vegetable oils were of reverse type. O/W type of

emulsion was possible only in case of benzene as internal phase. The emulsion produced was not very fine from the very beginning. The particle size varied from 61.75% (4 μ) to 9.75% (12 μ) on the first day and rapid coarsening took place on storage for 2 weeks only. This is clear from the low values of initial specific area values as given in Table 2. The emulsion produced was also not very stable. The stability coefficient value in this case can be compared with the stability coefficient of kerosene oil emulsion stabilised by guggal gum (Table 2). It can also be compared with the stability coefficient of the emulsion stabilised by Gonj gum obtained by Mukerjee and Shukla¹ in case of kerosene oil.

Rumi mastiki, also known as Rumi-mastungi⁸. Resinous exudation is used in solution as a filling for carious teeth.

With both vegetable oils it gave reverse type of emulsion (W/o). On the other hand kerosene oil and benzene produced o/w type of emulsions with very low initial specific areas (Table 2). The emulsion produced with kerosene oil was more stable with stability coefficient value equal to 17.53, which can be compared with the stability coefficient value of Neem gum¹.

Benzene produces most fine emulsions with dhavda gum as emulsifying agent. The sizes of the initial dispersion being 72.79% (4 μ), 18.13% (8 μ), 6.23% (12 μ) and 2.85% (16 μ). Coarsening took place from these sizes to 58.57% (4 μ); 29.28% (8 μ), 8.92% (12 μ) and 3.22% (16 μ) on one month's storage time and finally the percentage of particles of 4 μ , 8 μ , 12 μ and 16 μ was changed to 52.40, 27.14, 11.32, 5.83 respectively and a few particles of 20 μ (3.31%) also appeared. The oil separation started after 2nd week (2.8%). Kerosene oil produced the coarsest emulsion. The percentage of different sizes on the first day of preparation being 53.61% (4 μ), 26.00% (8 μ), 16.05% (12 μ) and 4.34 (16 μ), was reduced to 39.85% (4 μ), 25.95% (8 μ), 16.45 (12 μ), 11.20 (16 μ), respectively and due to coarsening particles of 20 μ size (6.55) also appeared.

The distribution of particle sizes was nearly similar in case of two vegetable oils used.

This emulsifier produced very stable O/W type of emulsions in all cases due to high values of viscosity of the suspension. This high viscosity of the suspension prevents the coalescence of the droplets thus confirming the greater stability to the system. This substance produced emulsions nearly of the same order as produced by gum karaya¹. The order of the stability coefficients of emulsions stabilised by this substance is as follows :

Olive oil > benzene > kerosene > castor oil

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